

Russia's Consideration of Afghanistan

Afganistan'a Rusya'dan Bakış

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Abstract

This study examines the Russian Federation's policies toward Afghanistan within the framework of security concerns, geopolitical interests, and regional power balances. Due to its historical background, geostrategic location, and persistent instability, Afghanistan occupies a central position in Russia's strategies aimed at safeguarding Central Asian security, combating transnational threats, and preserving its regional influence. Rather than limiting the analysis to bilateral relations, the study situates Russia's Afghanistan policy within a broader international context, considering its interactions and rivalries with major actors such as the United States, China, as well as regional powers including Pakistan, Iran, and the Central Asian states.

In the post-Soviet period, Russia's foreign policy has increasingly been shaped by the principles of multipolarity and Eurasianism, both of which play a decisive role in shaping Moscow's approach to Afghanistan. From this perspective, Afghanistan is perceived simultaneously as a source of potential security threats—such as terrorism, extremism, irregular migration, and drug trafficking—and as a strategic arena for promoting regional stability and limiting Western influence.

Methodologically, the study employs qualitative analysis based on official policy documents, strategic reports, and relevant academic literature to trace the evolution of Russia's Afghanistan policy. The findings suggest that Russia's engagement with Afghanistan cannot be reduced to short-term security considerations alone. Instead, it reflects a broader strategic vision aimed at consolidating Russia's position in the emerging multipolar international order. In this sense, Afghanistan represents both a challenge and an opportunity for Russia's regional and global ambitions.

Keywords: Russian Federation, Afghanistan, Foreign Policy, Eurasia, Regional Security

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Özet

Bu çalışma, Rusya Federasyonu'nun Afganistan'a yönelik politikalarını güvenlik kaygıları, jeopolitik çıkarlar ve bölgesel güç dengeleri bağlamında kapsamlı bir biçimde incelemektedir. Afganistan, tarihsel mirası, jeostratejik konumu ve kronik istikrarsızlığı nedeniyle Rusya'nın Orta Asya güvenliği, sınır aşan tehditlerle mücadele ve etki alanlarını koruma stratejilerinde kritik bir yer tutmaktadır. Çalışma, Rusya'nın Afganistan yaklaşımını yalnızca ikili ilişkiler çerçevesinde ele almakla yetinmemekte; aynı zamanda ABD, Çin, Pakistan, İran ve Orta Asya devletleri gibi aktörlerle yürütülen rekabet ve iş birliği dinamiklerini de analiz etmektedir.

Özellikle Sovyetler Birliği'nin dağılmasının ardından şekillenen Rus dış politikasında öne çıkan çok kutupluluk anlayışı ve Avrasyacı perspektif, Afganistan'a yönelik politikaların ideolojik ve stratejik arka planını oluşturmaktadır. Bu çerçevede Rusya, Afganistan'ı bir yandan radikal örgütler, düzensiz göç ve uyuşturucu ticareti gibi güvenlik tehditlerinin kaynağı olarak algılamak; diğer yandan bölgesel istikrarın sağlanması ve Batı etkisinin sınırlandırılması açısından önemli bir jeopolitik alan olarak değerlendirmektedir.

Çalışma, nitel yöntemlere dayalı olarak resmi belgeler, strateji metinleri ve ikincil kaynakların analizi yoluyla Rusya'nın Afganistan politikasının dönüşümünü ortaya koymayı amaçlamaktadır. Sonuç olarak makale, Rusya'nın Afganistan'a yönelik yaklaşımının yalnızca güvenlik merkezli değil, aynı zamanda küresel güç dengelerinde konumlanma arayışının bir parçası olduğunu savunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Rusya Federasyonu, Afganistan, Dış Politika, Avrasya, Bölgesel Güvenlik

Introduction

Foreign policy, in general, can be defined as the totality of actions that a country takes in response to events occurring outside its borders. In this respect, almost all states are obliged to make foreign policy moves in order to protect their national interests, ensure their national security, and eliminate all kinds of threats and attacks directed at them. This aim can be achieved by expanding the network of socio-political, socio-economic, geo-political, and geo-strategic relations (Yiğit, İnaç, and Güner 2006: 85). In this respect, developing cooperation with the actors who are parties to a problem and aiming to solve the problems peacefully with the least damage constitutes another aspect of foreign policy. States benefit from certain parameters to implement their foreign policies and reach their targeted goals within the time period they have determined in advance, in line with the possibilities. In the application of each country, foreign policy instruments show some changes according to the order of priority, according to the national interests and strategic goals of that country. In this context, elements such as "diplomacy", "propaganda", "economic methods" and "war" come to the fore as some of the basic elements of foreign policy. Although in theory, diplomacy is the most commonly used tool in all actions and methods, in practice, the benefits of diplomacy and negotiation are quite limited (Özdal ve Karca, 2018, s.31).

In this study, while analyzing Russia's foreign policy towards Afghanistan, we will take as a basis the issues we mentioned above regarding the basic instruments of foreign policy. When looking at Russian-Afghan relations, we will emphasize not only bilateral relations but also the new perspectives gained by these relations in the context of global politics. Starting from this point, Afghanistan has always been effective in determining the political and economic aspects of regional and global powers that separate Central Asia from South Asia due to its geographical location, and in the formation and conflict of geopolitical, geostrategic strategies and ideologies towards the region throughout the course of history (İnaç ve Erdoğan 2006, s.14). On the other hand, Afghanistan has mostly played a

critical role in the decline and rise of states or in the escalation of competitions and the dissolution of blocs. In this context, Russia's foreign policy towards Afghanistan has affected and continues to affect not only Afghanistan but also the international order together with the entire region in many ways. Indeed, when the issue is examined from the perspective of Russia's political ideal and Russian geopolitics, it is seen that Russia entered the region with an expansionist character and used the Eurasianist ideology in the meantime. However, Eurasianism is not just an innocent set of ideas as it seems, but an eclectic mentality that helps Europe as well as Russia establish a sphere of influence in the Central Asian region. Afghanistan is again at the heart of the "Eurasian" terminology produced by this mentality, and Afghanistan continues to be one of the important transportation and communication junctions in the Eurasian continent in the context of the Belt and Road project (Huntington, 2019, s.16-25).

1. Historical Background

Afghanistan, which was the home of Aryan tribes between 2000-1500 BC and was invaded by the Achaemenid Emperor Darius I in 516 BC and was invaded by the US on October 7, 2001, after the September 11 attacks, has been subjected to invasive attacks by powers claiming to be a global power throughout history. Afghanistan, which was honored with Islam during the reign of Hazrat Osman in 650, was ruled by the Turks until 1747 and from that date on transformed into the Durrani Empire. However, Afghanistan, which was a part of Turkestan in the series of wars known as the Great Game that emerged in the Eurasian geography between Russia and England, fell to England with the Dawran Treaty of 1893 (Rizazade, 2012, s.54-57).

Afghanistan, which was neighboring Tsarist Russia, the Chinese Empire, Iran led by the Pahlavi Dynasty's Great Reza Shah, and India under British rule, became the first country in the Asian continent to declare its independence on August 19, 1919, with the Treaty of Rawalpindi. However, Afghanistan, which could not save its lands from the ambitious ambitions of the invading powers, was gradually disintegrated in the context of the Eastern Question, which meant the sharing of Ottoman lands (Şeyhanlıoğlu, 2021, s.55-59). In other words, Afghanistan, which experienced the same fate as the Ottomans in the axis of the Eastern Question, did not only take land from Afghanistan with the establishment of a new state in the region as Pakistan by Britain in 1947 (Budak, 2019, s.121). This newly constructed artificial state, invented by England, was made a neighbor, and its ties with its old neighbor India were severed, leaving the Muslims living in India to the mercy of Buddhism, which was dominant in the country, and dividing the Muslims into four parts. The demographic structure of the Afghan society was also radically disrupted by the Dawrand border line, which has never been recognized by the Afghan State and nation since the day it was signed. As a result of this new construction, the Pashtuns and Baluch living in the provinces of "Subay Serhat" and "Subay Baluchistan" were uprooted from their homelands (İnaç, 2003, s.343). Thus, the foundations of a problem designed by England between Afghanistan and Pakistan were laid. Afghanistan, which had a border to the sea until 1947, was transformed into a landlocked state in time. With this strategic move, England blocked all communication channels of both Afghanistan and all Central Asian states with the world and consciously transformed the countries of the region into the sphere of influence of Russia's expansionist policy. Following the dissolution of the USSR in December 1991 and the declaration of independence of some countries from Soviet Russia, Afghanistan once again encountered brand new neighbors in the north and northwest (Oran, 2013, s.535-537). From the dissolution of the USSR to the present day, Afghanistan has been squeezed between six neighboring countries and the country's attempts at nationalization, development and opening up to the world have been thwarted and the means and means of liberation have been Access to their equipment has been made impossible in a planned manner.

2. Geopolitical Theories and Tsarist Russia's Foreign Policy in Afghanistan (1838-1919)

In the 19th century, the hegemonic competition struggle in Asia, the "Great Game", continued between Tsarist Russia and England, centered in Afghanistan, which was part of the broad definition of the Middle East. Before the signing of the 1907 Entente between Great Britain and Tsarist Russia, which ended the ongoing competition struggle and determined the spheres of influence, political and military experts pondered over who would dominate the world order and how to gain strategic superiority. Experts who conducted studies on the subject have put forward a number of geopolitical theories in determining strategic centers of attraction.

Indeed, three years before the 1907 British-Russian Entente, in 1904, British Geographer Halford John Mackinder gave a lecture titled "The Geographical Axis of History". Also known as the Land Dominance Theory, Mackinder's geopolitical theory named the continents of Africa, Asia, and Europe (Afro-Eurasia) as the "World Island" and argued that the strategic center of gravity of the world in terms of geopolitics was the Afro-Eurasian region (Delanty 2013, s.142). He defined the great plain extending between Eastern Siberia and the Volga basin, which is cut by the Ural Mountains, as the Heartland. He described the surrounding countries of Austria, the Ottoman Empire, Germany, India, and China, as the "Inner Crescent" or the Border Belt. He defined the states outside the Inner Crescent, including the United States of America (USA), England, Australia, Canada, Japan, and South Africa, as the "Outer Crescent" by placing them in the third box he imagined in his mental world (Oran, 2013, s.561-563). In short, Mackinder actually wanted to express the following with his theory of domination. The power that dominates the east of Europe also has the effect of controlling the central region, the Heartland. The power that dominates the Heartland also gains the power to control and govern the world island. Similarly, the power that dominates the world island will also gain the power to control the entire world.

From this point of view, sovereignty is a subject closely related to the provision of security and its acceptance and sustainability, and security is a phenomenon that emerges and makes its presence felt by eliminating all current and potential threats. Therefore, in our humble opinion, the following observation we have made is quite appropriate. The power that dominates Eastern Europe threatens the countries in its heartland. The power that dominates the Heartland region becomes a power that threatens the world island, and a power that dominates the world island becomes a power that threatens the entire world. Indeed, Mackinder's Theory of Land Sovereignty found resonance in Germany, which he saw as a threat, rather than in England, the source country. On the other hand, Mackinder's Theory was developed by the German General Karl Haushofer and manifested itself in Nazi Germany in the form of the Living Space (Lebensraum) political idea (Tutar, İnaç and Güner 2006, s.285).

The name that developed Mackinder's theory, a British geopolitician, in America who revised it in the context of national interests was Nicolas Spykman. First of all, Spykman, an American political scientist, tried to build Mackinder's theory, which was built on three pillars, on two legs. Based on the parameters of future industrial and demographic growth, Spykman defined the heartland of the Central Asian region, which Brzezinski described as the Eurasian Balkans in his work *The Grand Chessboard*, as the strategic center of gravity of the global power, starting from the Gulf region and extending around India, as the Rim Belt (Yıldırım, 2018, s.9-20). Therefore, according to Spykman, a power that controls the Rim Belt rules Eurasia, and the one that dominates Eurasia controls the world. The common point of Spykman's theory, which guides strategic moves in the US foreign policy, and Mackinder's theory, which determines the British strategy, is the aim of coping with the threatening and potential rival power (Brzezinski, 2018, s.190-209).

In light of what we have explained above, it should be stated that when needs, goals, and priorities change, geopolitical and geoeconomic strategies are inevitably subject to change. In other words, geopolitical theory in the struggle for dominance prioritizes seizing the strategic center of gravity of a threatening or potential rival power. Starting from this point, Tsarist Russia, headed by Peter the Great, shaped its foreign policy towards the Balkans through the ideology of Pan-Slavism, or the ideology of uniting the Slavic race under a single political roof. In addition, Tsarist Russia, which aimed to get into hot waters and narrow down the Ottoman sphere of influence, aimed to distance the Ottomans from Europe in the context of the Eastern Question with the support of other European countries. Similarly, in the east, it shaped its regional policy towards Central Asia on factors such as keeping England away from Central Asia and reaching warm waters, in the context of the process that was introduced to the literature by Lord Salisbury in 1869, symbolizing the competitive struggle between England and Russia and went down in history as the Great Game concept (İnaç 2007, s.27).

Afghanistan, which was in a key position for Tsarist Russia to reach warm waters and also served as the security gate of Central Asia, which was historically seen as a "backyard", was subjected to colonial attacks three times until the Declaration of Independence. Just as the Ottoman Empire was not intended to be kept as a monolithic power at that time, efforts were made in the Great Game initiated by England and Russia not to leave Afghanistan under the control of a single state (Arı, 2005, s.2-15). In short, Russia's foreign policy towards Afghanistan within the framework of the Great Game, on the one hand, made the country vulnerable to British attacks, on the other hand, it played a key role in reshaping the country's borders. As a logical extension of this policy, it created the necessary ground to invade Afghanistan in 1979 and did not provide assistance to Afghanistan in the Afghan-British wars.

3. Foreign Policy of the USSR Towards Afghanistan (1919-1979)

The Bolshevik Revolution, which took place between 1917 and 1921, with the contribution of the nationalist ideology brought by the French Revolution of 1789 and the influence of the First World War, paved the way for the establishment of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on December 30, 1922, in the lands of Tsarist Russia, after the internal conflicts were calmed.

While England accepted its defeat with the Treaty of Rawalpindi, the Afghan people declared their independence under the leadership of King Amanullah Khan on August 19, 1919. After independence, the Bolsheviks, who came to power through the revolution, took advantage of the opportunity to strengthen the legitimacy of their existence and to draw Afghanistan to their side and declared that they officially recognized Afghanistan on March 27, 1919. Although the USSR apparently used the diplomatic element, one of the basic elements of foreign policy, as a tool to strengthen relations with Afghanistan, in fact, the USSR's foreign policy towards Afghanistan was first shaped by the other basic tool of foreign policy, the economic element.

Indeed, the Russian-Afghan relationship, which was purified from socialist ideology and built on economic foundations, naturally could not prevent Afghanistan from recognizing the TBMM government with the Turkish-Afghan Friendship Treaty dated March 1, 1921 (Şeyhanlıoğlu, 2021, s.55-59). On the other hand, the Basmachi movement, which referred to themselves as Korbaşi and took place between 1918 and 1934, attempted to implement a collectivization policy with the aim of restructuring the agricultural sector from 1928 to 1935 after Stalin came to power, causing a wave of migration from Central Asia to Afghanistan and attempting to design the demographic structure of the region and Afghanistan (Erman, 2018, s.25-30). Secondly, the USSR wanted to take the relations to a higher level by taking advantage of the Cooperation and Friendship Treaty signed with Afghanistan on September 12, 1919, and the Afghan King's desire to make radical reforms, and put

the other basic tool of foreign policy, the propaganda machine, into action in order to put Afghanistan under ideological influence and pressure. An example of this is Lenin's letter to King Amanullah Khan stating that Russia was on the side of the peasant and working class, and his desire to fight against imperialism in the Revolutionary Declaration. However, in the first twenty years of its independence, Afghanistan preferred to develop relations with many countries, especially Türkiye and Germany, in order to protect itself from the threats of the USSR and the British, and not to fall into the sphere of influence of the USSR, and to be able to implement reforms in social and political life, and followed a multifaceted policy towards this end (İnaç, 2005b, s.143).

However, the USSR, which was trying to achieve its foreign policy goals with the doctrine of "Socialism in One Country", perceived the opening of its neighbor Afghanistan to the outside world as a future threat. Afghanistan's integration with Europe outside the ideological orbit of socialism would both set a precedent for the Central Asian countries and would lead to the emergence of new problems in terms of the USSR's economic and strategic goals in Afghanistan. In this respect, the USSR embarked on a project to establish a satellite government that would support itself in Afghanistan (İnaç, 2005a, s.64). Its expectations from this government were to benefit from Afghanistan's geopolitical location and economic opportunities and to expand and strengthen its Socialist Bloc. In addition, keeping the Central Asian countries, which it saw as its backyard, under control and preventing the geopolitical area defined in the context of Eurasianism ideology from turning into an area of influence and impact of European powers were among the duties of this satellite 'communist' Afghan government.

In other words, the USSR, just like its rival England, has associated Afghanistan with the phenomenon of globalization and turned it into a planned problem of the struggle for dominance of global powers. In addition, the USSR, which guided its foreign policy with the doctrine of "Socialism in One Country" in the 20th century, gave a century's advance to Great Britain, the pioneer of the colonialist ideology of Tsarist Russia, which it succeeded, in terms of ideological dominance, and virtually handed Afghanistan over to another. Indeed, when the Soviet Union could not achieve its strategic goals during the Cold War with its efforts to coalify Afghanistan on the axis of the doctrine of socialism in one country and through the pro-USSR communist Afghan regime it brought to power, it invaded Afghanistan on December 24, 1979, by activating the other fundamental element of foreign policy, the war (İnaç ve Sada, 2021, s.148-169). The USSR, which pushed Afghanistan into a tragicomic process that still continues today, was defeated by the mujahideen with the support of the Islamic World and the Western World and was forced to withdraw from the country with the 1989 Geneva Agreement.

The USSR, which forced one-third of the country's population to migrate, paved the way for the Afghan civil war, and ethnic conflicts and disrupted the Afghan nation-building process, but could not prevent the cost of its foreign policy towards Afghanistan from being even heavier in the West, even political changes such as Gorbachev's Glasnost (Openness-Transparency) and Perestroika (Restructuring). As a result, the USSR's foreign policy towards Afghanistan could not keep Afghanistan in its hands and did not serve its dreams of landing in hot water (Burget 2017, s.331). On the contrary, the USSR's foreign policy towards Afghanistan served to the disintegration of the USSR into 15 countries on December 25, 1991, the independence of the Central Asian, South Caucasian, Baltic, and East Central European countries, the burning of the bipolar world order and the USA becoming the world's sole superpower. Therefore, history has affected Russia's foreign policy, security policy, geopolitics, and political thought, as well as Russia's policy towards Afghanistan. Based on this, it can be seen that Russia's foreign policy towards Afghanistan has different orientations in different periods (Zholdosbek Kyzy 2018, s.1-2).

As a result, Russia has gradually implemented the main parameters mentioned above in its foreign policy towards Afghanistan. In other words, although Russia has used "Soft Power" and "Hard Power" in Afghanistan, it has not achieved the goals it had previously set, and despite all the failures, it has not given up its insidious imperialist ambitions toward Central Asia in general and Afghanistan in particular (Armaoğlu, 2014, s.377-379). Therefore, the Russians' interest in Afghanistan and their fear of the Afghan nation started in the period of Tsarist Russia and still continues in Putin's Russia.

4. Foreign Policy of the Russian Federation towards Afghanistan (1992-2023)

According to the Geneva Convention of 1989, the Red Army was forced to leave Afghanistan. However, the inability of international and supranational structures such as the UN, OSCE, and EU to solve the problems in Afghanistan, the country was almost pushed towards isolation. On the other hand, the country was left to the sphere of influence and influence of Saudi Arabia and Pakistan under the leadership of the USA. At that time, the foreign policies of Saudi Arabia and Pakistan towards Afghanistan inevitably included Iran, which saw it as a threat to its own national security, in the competition to expand its sphere of influence in Afghanistan (Eğittepe, 2017, s.7).

Of course, the only motivation behind Iran's policy of expanding its sphere of influence and impact in Afghanistan, which sees Afghanistan as close to itself in terms of language, sect, and race, is not limited to preemptive concerns against the USSR. Therefore, after the end of the Cold War and the dissolution of the USSR, the United States, which provided nearly 3 billion dollars of weapons to the Mujahideen in the Russo-Afghan War, waited until the September 11 attacks to invade Afghanistan with its imperial logic as the world's sole hegemonic power (Osmanoğlu, 1990, s.333). In the new unipolar world order that emerged after the dissolution of the USSR, the Russian Federation (RF), the successor of the Soviet Union, joined the international system with a federated state structure. After the end of the war, the Russian Federation accelerated its foreign policy efforts in order to overcome the remaining internal and external problems. From 1991 to the present, the Russian system of thought, geopolitical security, and ensuring political and economic stability have been important priorities in the construction of Russian foreign policy. However, Russia's Afghanistan policy has been shaped around parameters such as preventing and eliminating geopolitical and geostrategic threats in the Eurasian context, integrating with the free market economy of the West, and equipping the army with modern technological military equipment (Alagöz ve Kandemir, s.2015).

It is possible to say that Russian foreign policy during the Boris Yeltsin era was generally a pro-Western policy that ended the USSR's imperialist expansionist policy in order to restore relations with the West. Indeed, the aim of this policy, which ended its nuclear competition in order to strengthen strategic cooperation with the USA, was to develop cooperation with international organizations such as NATO, UNSC, ODT, and G-7. With the appointment of Yevgeniy Primakov as foreign minister in 1996, Russia abandoned its one-sided foreign policy and began to pursue a multi-sided foreign policy. On the other hand, one of the most important factors in the change of Russia's foreign policy approach is the failure of the USA and international organizations to do their part to stop the internal conflicts in Afghanistan, which has been pushed into isolation. Another parameter that played a vital role in Russia's adoption of this new political approach was undoubtedly the silence of the United States regarding the official recognition of the Taliban, which took over Afghanistan in 1996, by Pakistan, Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates (Zholdoshbek Kyzy, 2018, s.1-2).

Therefore, following the terrorist attacks of September 11, the United States of America initiated an invasion mobilization attempt against Afghanistan under the umbrella of NATO, which also included the EU, the UN, and many other international organizations. Consequently, the People's Republic of

China, which joined the World Trade Organization in 2001 and is Afghanistan's northeastern neighbor, has not opposed the US's attack on Afghanistan by implementing the policy of opening up to the world, which it has been pursuing since Deng-Xiaoping came to power in 1976, in order to develop the stages of becoming a regional power and to realize its dream of a new world order to be established in the 21st century. Russia has declared that it is in favor of maintaining peace and security in the international order and that it is not a threat to the international order, and has also remained silent and tacitly supported the US invasion of Afghanistan, which it associates with the concept of international relations in order to strengthen its political image.

Thus Boris Yeltsin, who came to power for the first time in Russian political history on June 12, 1991, by popular vote, pursued a foreign policy that envisioned pluralism in politics and a free market policy in the economy. In short, it is possible to say that Yeltsin was greatly influenced by the Atlanticist Approach in pursuing a pro-Western foreign policy. Indeed, advocates of the Atlanticist Approach historically claim that Russia is an inseparable part of European civilization and point to the East as a threat. Therefore, this approach insists on Russia pursuing a pro-Western foreign policy in order to develop its cooperation with Western institutions and internalize European values, to help Russia develop and protect itself from threats from the East. (Age: 3-6). As part of his pro-Western foreign policy, Yeltsin abandoned traditional USSR friends such as China, Cuba, and Vietnam, because Russia focused on proving that it was not only a collaborator of the West but also a reliable friend.

Another approach that influenced Yeltsin's foreign policy was the Western Idealist Approach, which put forward the thesis that totalitarian regimes could only be changed and transformed with Western values and that the constructive values of the Russian identity were articulated with Western values in historical depths. Although Russia's pro-Western foreign policy had long transformed the conflict between the US and Russia into an alliance, Yeltsin clearly stated that he was not satisfied with the pro-Western policy during his resignation. Therefore, the pro-Western policy pursued by Yeltsin's Russia had no place for traditional friends of the USSR, and naturally, considering Afghanistan as a friend did not quite match the conjunctural reality. When we turn to Putin's Russia's foreign policy, when we look at the approaches that influenced this policy, we come across approaches such as the anti-Western Pragmatist Approach and the Neo-Eurasianist Approach.

After the end of the Andrey Kozirev period, Yevgeny Maksimovich Primakov, who assumed the duty of foreign affairs, emphasized that the West and the US should be kept away from the geography where Russia's national interests existed, also under the influence of the Eurasianist Approach. On the other hand, Primakov pointed to the Post-Soviet area as an area of competition with the West and the US, while defining it as an area that should be protected from the mentioned powers of its immediate surroundings (Elnur, 2013, s.92). In other words, he emphasized that in order to create a balance against the US hegemony in Russian geopolitics, it was essential to focus on re-developing relations with these states, primarily the Middle East, the Balkans, Eastern Europe, the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), Cuba and North Korea, which were described as traditional friends. With the Eurasianist Approach becoming the dominant approach in Russian foreign policy, it also led to the loss of the strategic superiority of the Atlanticist Approach in Russian foreign policy.

The Eurasianist Approach describes everything produced by the West as evil and does not accept that Russia is neither Western nor Eastern and claims that it has its own identity structure and civilizational values (Özkan 2019, s.1748). In other words, unlike the Atlanticist approach, it is an approach that defines the West as the greatest source of threat and consents to the existence of a unified structure in the context of Slavic, Mongolian and Turkish ethnicity, or rather the concept of "super ethnos", and its dominance in the continent. Eurasian Geopolitics is an approach that tries to consolidate sovereignty with its bipolar order in the triangle of Russia, Germany, and France in the West and

Delhi, Beijing, and Moscow in the East (Akçapa 2022, s.1-9). Names such as Alexander Dugin, A. Panarin, and M. Titarenko, who are known as the founding fathers of the approach, have laid the foundation for abandoning the West-centered Eastern policy with this approach and pursuing an East-centered Western policy. In other words, this approach is not far removed from the near-environment policy. Those who put forward the Anti-Western Pragmatist approach, unlike the Western Pragmatist approach, have given importance to a policy method based on the zero-sum style, which prioritizes one side gaining while the other loses, instead of the win-win principle in the economy.

On the other hand, it is obvious that foreign policy is not a phenomenon that can be explained solely by economic interests. In addition to the economy, foreign policy cannot be considered separately from mission, norms, interests, and ideals. In summary, the most important factor that has brought new dimensions to Russian foreign policy has been the US's foreign policy towards the region based on Afghanistan. The multifaceted Russian foreign policy that formed the basis of Vladimir Putin's foreign policy concept, which came to power in the 2000s, has also brought with it rumors of becoming a superpower again. When we consider Russian foreign policy in terms of the "Near Abroad Doctrine", we witness that Russia, with this doctrine, has pursued an active foreign policy not only towards the "Post-Soviet" states but also including the Middle East, including Afghanistan (Zholdosbek Kyzy, 2018, s.1-2).

With Putin coming to power, the change and diversification of strategies in Russian foreign policy can be described as the recovery and revival process of Russian foreign policy from 1990 to 2000. Russian foreign policy, which has continued from 2000 to the present day, includes foreign policy moves that provide gains in many areas such as military, political, and economic, a leap in weapons and nuclear energy, and a certain degree of energy control, especially in oil and natural gas. A pragmatist foreign policy that believes that no one else is responsible for expanding the geopolitical area and ensuring security in the Eurasian region and aims to become a global power with self-confidence accompanies these moves. Therefore, Russian foreign policy, which was activated after the US invasion of Iraq in 2003, turned into an aggressive foreign policy when Russian military units invaded Georgia on August 8, 2008. Russia's increasingly aggressive foreign policy was transformed into an aggressive foreign policy with the annexation of Crimea in 2014, and with the attack on Ukraine on February 22, 2022, Putin's Russia has clearly demonstrated in practice that it has not abandoned the expansionist foreign policy of the Soviet era.

Therefore, Putin Russia's apparent expansionist foreign policy, which has historically seen the Central Asian region as its backyard and has remained indifferent to it, is not only incompatible with the geopolitical and geoeconomic principles defended by the Eurasianist approach that guides Russian foreign policy but also contradicts the parameters of Russian identity construction envisaged by this approach. From this point of view, just as Russia's policy towards Central Asian countries guides its Afghanistan policy, Afghanistan's policy towards Western states and Russia also guides Russia's policy towards Central Asian countries (İnaç, 2014, s.49).

Lavrov, the foreign minister of Putin's Russia, who consented to the US invasion of Afghanistan and included the Taliban in the terrorist list in 2003, used the expression "We are ready to cooperate in all constructive matters in Afghanistan" at the Afghanistan conference held in Moscow on March 27, 2009, which is also an expression of the transformation of Russia's foreign policy towards Afghanistan. Indeed, after this date, while continuing its economic and diplomatic relations with the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, on the one hand, it did not refrain from selling arms to the Taliban and developing relations. Starting from this point, with this policy transformation, Russia has in a sense pursued a revanchist policy by providing the Taliban with the same arms support that the US provided to the mujahideen in the Russo-Afghan War (Akkurt, 2005, s.249-252). Indeed, the lack of the ability and capacity of foreign policy decision-makers who hold political authority in Afghanistan and other Central Asian countries to transform the political and economic crises in the region to their

advantage has served to make these countries fall victim to the expansionist policies of Eastern and Western hegemonic powers for three centuries.

On the other hand, the inadequacy of regional states in transforming and managing crises to their advantage, and the pragmatist and expansionist policies of global and regional powers towards the region are other factors in transforming the region from an area of competition to an area of chaos. Because power does not accept a vacuum, and a vacuum also attracts power. Based on this principle, when any global power attempts to occupy Afghanistan, it has condemned the traditional regional powers in the region to follow a policy of closure or collaboration. Similarly, when the occupying powers leave Afghanistan, the policy of regional powers towards Afghanistan manifests itself in two new ways.

Firstly, regional powers that have been on the alert every century to fill the power vacuum in Afghanistan are pursuing a competitive foreign policy towards Afghanistan, while secondly, regional powers are pursuing a security policy to protect their own national interests and achieve their strategic goals (Özkan 2022a, s.149). Based on this, throughout history, Afghanistan has been stripped of its independence as a result of the expansionist policies of occupying powers, and the country has been transformed into a center of chaos and crises, while regional powers have undermined the country's nation-building process as a result of their competitive and security policies towards the country, and also disrupted the country's development and integration into the international system. Consequently, it did not capture Kabul for the second time on August 15, 2021. At the same time, it has revealed that the reasons for the US's invasion of Afghanistan 20 years ago do not coincide with the facts. On the other hand, the power vacuum that emerged in the country after the US left Afghanistan mobilized regional powers (Bilgin, 2004, s.54-61).

In the context of competitive and security-oriented political approaches, states that want to expand their sphere of influence in Afghanistan and the Central Asian region and achieve their strategic goals are trying to change paradigms in terms of their foreign policy concepts and diversify risk and threat areas in order to protect vital interests and to draw them to the area where they achieve a definitive victory in the power struggle. After the US, the first effective power in Afghanistan for the Taliban is undoubtedly the People's Republic of China, followed by Putin's Russia in second place. Indeed, Putin's Russia carried out a joint military exercise with Uzbekistan and Tajikistan, which started on the northern border of Afghanistan 10 days before the Taliban took over Kabul within the framework of the Collective Security Treaty and ended on August 10, 2021, while continuing its diplomatic relations with the Taliban administration by keeping its embassy in Kabul, which is under Taliban control, open (Özkan, 2022b, s.241).

In summary, although Russia's approach towards Afghanistan includes many different dynamics after the US-NATO forces left Afghanistan, the concept of security has become more prominent in Russia's foreign policy towards Afghanistan. The question of what the Kremlin aims to achieve with this security policy, which seeks its own national security in the security of its neighbors and describes Afghanistan, which is the neighbor of its neighbors, as a threat center, comes to mind. While Putin's Russia, which has seen Central Asia as its backyard throughout history, sees the possible expansion policy of NATO and the EU in the West as a threat, in Central Asia, Türkiye's policy of opening up to Central Asia and China's expansionist policy towards the region, which is expanding day by day in the context of the Belt and Road Project, have virtually cornered Russia. Although Afghanistan has not directly threatened Russia throughout history, Russia is trying to make regional countries compatible with the security concept it has created by conducting perception operations in the context of the security threat discourse by drawing the priority needs of the countries in the region to the security area. On the other hand, by trying to prove through perception operations that the new

security policy it has developed coincides with its conjectural reality, it actually aims to design the policies of these countries towards Afghanistan.

In other words, Russia is trying to add to itself through the military channel, since the Central Asian countries that gained independence after the collapse of the USSR could not be politically integrated with it, with the security policy it has implemented on the Afghanistan-centered security threat discourse. In other words, it aims to stop the integration process of the Central Asian Turkic Republics, which are trying to integrate with the West through Türkiye and to recover its economy, which is deteriorating day by day, by selling its own weapons industry products to these countries. In short, keeping Afghanistan, which is the gateway of Central Asia to the international seas and the world, away is, first and foremost, a requirement of Russia's Nearby Doctrine. Therefore, the convenient concept that Russia uses to neutralize all arguments and instruments that will help Central Asia's integration process with the West is the security threat discourse.

Russia aims to restore the image of Russia damaged by the collapse of the Soviet Union by taking into account the security threat discourse and the geopolitical and geostrategic location of Afghanistan. Therefore, Russia's security-based Central Asia-centered expansion policy towards Afghanistan is to cover up the current realities with perception operations and to achieve the possible goals it aims for in the context of Eurasian geopolitics. Russia uses propaganda and military tools rather than economic and diplomatic methods to achieve the goals it has determined with this policy. Russia benefits from formations and organizations such as the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO), the Eurasian Economic Union (EEU), and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) in the implementation of its pragmatism and security-oriented policy towards Afghanistan (Akçapa, 2022, s.1-9).

The security-based policies pursued by global and regional powers and Afghanistan's bordering states towards Afghanistan do not match the realities, and they also contradict the discourse of these states being in favor of stability in Afghanistan. If Afghanistan, along with six neighboring states, is considered a threat to the security of the region and the international system by global and regional powers, then it is an indispensable factor to face the realities with a holistic approach. For this, it is vital to answer questions such as what are the factors that make Afghanistan a threat, where they originate from, where and from what they are fed, with a consistent consciousness that envisages transparency. Secondly, the security-oriented policies pursued by these states interested in the region and Afghanistan should be reviewed once again and investigated whether they match the realities. On the other hand, it is necessary to question whether the approaches adopted regarding these policies, the tools, and methods used in foreign policies, as well as the targets aimed with these policies, destabilize Afghanistan, radicalize it, and threaten national, regional, and global peace and security.

If we were to answer these questions objectively, it is a well-known fact that Russia has been a country that has pursued imperialist and expansionist goals since the day it entered the historical scene, as well as following a policy of domination and expansion. It is also an undeniable reality that if Afghanistan followed an expansionist policy at certain turning points in history before the beginning of the Great Era, its main target was not the north of the country but the south. Therefore, Afghanistan has never directly threatened either the Central Asian region or Russia throughout history. Indeed, Afghanistan, which was made the center of the power struggle between Russia and England during the Great Game, was directly invaded by Russia on December 24, 1979. On the other hand, by defeating the Russian Red Armies, the people of Afghanistan helped the Central Asian countries complete their independence processes by accelerating the dissolution of the USSR. However, Afghanistan has been subjected to attacks by regional and global powers at every stage of history, regardless of its geographical aspect, and has also been the victim of political approaches that serve the purposes of the imperialist circles of its border neighbors in the last 43 years (Haviland, 2002, s.178).

Another important point that should be underlined regarding the subject is that, after the Great Game was put into effect in Afghanistan, unfortunately, it has not reached the capacity to directly threaten any country in the region, especially its neighboring countries, in terms of security and economy. Not only has it not reached such a power, but the Afghan people have been able to repel the invasion attempts against Afghanistan with the arms and economic aid of foreign states. Because historians, political scientists, and strategists cannot claim anything contrary to what we say, because such a claim does not coincide with the facts experienced in history. In other words, Russia is at the forefront of the powers that have turned Afghanistan into a center of crisis with its military and ideological attacks that have undermined the nation-building process of Afghanistan and pushed the country into unbearable tragicomic problems.

The main architect of the chronic problems that Afghanistan is struggling with today is undoubtedly England, which has confined the country to its land borders by taking away its access to international seas. Another important issue is that all occupying forces use the lands of neighboring countries while attempting to invade Afghanistan. The USA invaded Afghanistan citing the September 11 attacks as a pretext. However, unfortunately, no concrete document has yet been produced regarding the claims that the USA has made, which are nothing more than rhetoric. The USA killed Osama Bin Laden, the number one perpetrator of the September 11 attacks, in an operation it conducted in the town of "Abbotabad" near the capital of Pakistan on May 1, 2011. Based on this, Afghanistan's lands have been used for the first time since its independence by a foreign state against another foreign state during this operation. However, the same US requesting a guarantee from the Taliban regarding the use of Afghan territory for itself and its strategic partners in the Doha Peace Agreement signed with the Taliban in Doha, the capital of Qatar, on February 29, 2020, is an example of a contradiction that is not compatible with the facts (Bilgin, 2004, s.54-61).

Therefore, whatever the reason, regional and global powers, including Afghanistan's neighboring countries, have a great interest in Afghanistan's territory and politics. While it is obvious that all these sides we mentioned are much stronger than today's Afghanistan in every sense, and while they express on every platform that they are in favor of a stable Afghanistan and against terrorist organizations, how is it that these circles, hold themselves responsible for threats to the international system and the responsibility for world peace, cannot find a solution to the Afghanistan problem? Could it be that they are trying to exhaust all the solutions to find a solution to the country's problems by saying that they are in favor of stability in Afghanistan, and are seeking their own stability in Afghanistan's instability and the continuation of their partnership in Afghanistan's problems?

If this is not the case, how can Afghanistan, which is surrounded by six powerful neighboring states and has been a cornerstone for regional and global powers confined to its land borders since 1974 in achieving their geopolitical and geostrategic goals, threaten international order, peace, and security? In other words, how can Afghanistan be portrayed as an actor capable of threatening Russia or its neighbors, while the Taliban government, which recaptured Afghanistan on August 15, 2021, is under siege and even the official recognition of the government is up to the US?

In other words, how can a state whose national wealth has been frozen by the US break this blockade, which is strictly implemented by the world, on its own from the inside, without receiving help from other neighboring and regional powers? The US and Western countries have been imposing a travel ban on high-level officials of the Taliban administration since 2022. No one attended the meeting of neighboring countries of Afghanistan held in Samarkand, Uzbekistan on April 13, 2023, or the UN-led conference on Afghanistan, which was closed to the press in Doha. At the Shanghai Cooperation Organization Defense Ministers meeting on April 23, 2023, the Russian Defense Minister claimed that extremist groups such as ISIS, Al Qaeda, the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan, and the Islamic Movement of East Turkestan could infiltrate Central Asia. However, although all of these groups he

mentioned originated from Central Asia and the Middle East, the Russian Defense Minister did not mention which country these groups entered Afghanistan from and accused the US of expanding its military influence in the region.

5. Conclusion

In light of the information we have mentioned above, we can say that Russia is trying to cut off Afghanistan's communication channels with its northern Muslim neighbors in order to prevent 30 million Muslims living within its territory from contacting the Taliban. On the other hand, Afghanistan, which has no diplomatic relations with the world, whose communication channels with other countries of the world are closed, and which only tries to survive with international aid, is a country that lacks the capacity to threaten any neighboring state, especially Russia. It is obvious that the real element threatening Russia's national interests and geopolitical security is not Afghanistan but other regional powers, especially the USA. Again, in light of the information we have mentioned above, it is possible to state that Afghanistan, which has been deliberately excluded from the international political arena and condemned to isolationist policies, is again being dragged into an environment of chaos in the near future as a result of meetings held behind closed doors. In short, the pragmatic security-oriented political stance it pursues towards Afghanistan, which is based on the security threat discourse, is nothing more than a reflection of Russia's imperialist expansionist policy towards the region.

The international conjuncture, which plays an active role in activating internal and external dynamics that lead to cracks and disruptions in the national and international political order, is one of the important elements of a subject that should be addressed in terms of socio-political analysis. Indeed, just as the political history of nations affects world political history, world political history has also played and continues to play an important role in changing the destinies of nations. Because, since the establishment of the Westphalia Peace Treaty system, the existence of a nation that has reached the consciousness of the construction of national identity, which is the sole source of legitimacy of the nation-state, national sovereignty, and political authority, is a fact accepted by everyone (İnaç ve Ünal, 2013, s.229). As a result, Afghanistan, which has been the target of political and military strategies in every century, has been dragged into a socio-economic crisis with the political approaches followed by Russia and the USA. Beyond this, the source of legitimacy of national sovereignty and political authority has been destroyed, and it has been reduced to a state of inability to bring both sides together and to form a central state structure with the divide-and-rule method. Indeed, we see the latest example of this in China's competitive foreign policy based on economics accompanied by diplomatic tools towards Afghanistan in the new world order of the 21st century. Another striking example is Russia's security-oriented foreign policy implemented through its neighbors based on the security threat discourse centered on Afghanistan. Although Russia's security-oriented foreign policy initially manifested itself as a defensive policy prioritizing the protection of national security through the security threat discourse, it can be shown that such a policy transformed into an aggressive policy in the final stage. These examples alone already provide us with signs that Afghanistan will be pushed into chaos again in the not-so-distant future.

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